

Colour variations in *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (DSI/NRF Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda)

Cyrtophora citricola Forsskål (1775) the tropical tent-web spider exhibits morphological polymorphism, primarily in colouration of body patterns. Individuals show a wide range of colours—from black-and-white patterns to various shades of brown and reddish brown. Males are often nearly black, while females tend to be more brownish with cryptic leaf-like markings. This variation is not just sexual dimorphism but also occurs among females, suggesting adaptive polymorphism for camouflage in different habitats. Studies in South Africa found diverse abdominal shapes and colour patterns among specimens, indicating significant intraspecific variation (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022).

In a study by Franzini *et al.* (2013) fresh and museum specimens sampled from 2006 to 2011 were used looking at combined DNA data - the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (CO1) and nuclear histone H3 genes - with morphological features of the genitalia to investigate the question whether there is only a single species present in South Africa.

They found at least two genetically distinct lineages in South Africa that correlate with differences in colour and genital morphology. *Cyrtophora citricola* shows clear polymorphism in colour and morphology and these variations are linked to ecological adaptation and may play a role in its success as a widespread, colonial orb-weaver. The second species in South Africa turn out to be *Cyrtophora petersi* Karsch, 1878.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & WEBB P. 2022. *The Araneidae of South Africa. part 1 (A-C)*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 74 pp. <https://doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326922>

FRANZINI P.Z.N., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., YESSOUFOU K. & VAN DER BANK H. 2013. Mitochondrial, genomic DNA and morphological data indicate that more than one species of *Cyrtophora* (Araneae: Araneidae) exists in South Africa. *International Journal of Modern Biological Research* 1: 21–34.

Cyrtophora citricola showing the morphological polymorphism, in colouration of body patterns. Credits: Peter Webb.

Cyrtophora citricola epigyne. Credit: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman

Cyrtophora petersi female from Malelane. Credit: P. Stephan.